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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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EXAMINATION OF ISLAMIC TAKAFUL INSURANCE MODEL IN NIGERIA VIS-À-VIS THE POWERS OF THE NATIONAL INSURANCE COMMISSION (NAICOM)

By

*Ochenehi Dominic Sunday**, *Mohammed Bashir Saidu***,

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ABSTRACT

This work examines the various Takaful Insurance models permissible in Nigeria to wit: Mudarabah meaning profit-sharing, Wakalah - agency and Wakalah-Mudarabah - hybrid. The Takaful guidelines also require that every operation have Sharia Council - Advisory Council of Experts to guide the operation and to ensure that all Sharia decisions and views are made by the Council. Takaful is a branded Islamic Insurance policy that is based on Sharia or Islamic religious law meaning that members are expected to cooperate with the intention to protect one another, Takaful policies cover life, health and other general insurance needs. The work also examines the powers and responsibilities of NAICOM in the registration and licensing of its operation. Takaful Insurance companies are introduced to primarily serve as alternative to the conventional insurance companies which are generally believed to go against Islamic principles and restrictions on interest, gambling and uncertainty which are not acceptable norms in Islam. This work aims to explore, with the support of statutes, case laws, and available texts as primary and secondary sources, along with data in the field as part of the research methodology, the various models operating in Nigeria. It specifically investigates the structure, functioning, and application of Takaful models in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Takaful Models, NAICOM, Powers, Operations and Responsibilities*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Practice of Takaful Insurance in Nigeria

Insurance generally is a situation where a party who suffers setback is brought back to his position before the occurrence of the loss. It is a contract that is represented by a policy in which a policy holder receives financial protection or reimbursement against losses from an insurance company. The main purpose of takaful under Islamic law is not only the provision of guarantee but also to bring equity to all parties involved and the objective of the contract is to help the participants through difficult times. As such, while profit earning is not the main goal of takaful, sharing of profits generated is acceptable.¹

Most importantly, at the center of every takaful system are the takaful operators and the participants. While the takaful operator manages and administers the takaful fund, the participants on the other hand own the takaful fund. In other words, the participants are the investors. In essence, while the actual ownership of the takaful fund lies with the participants, the fund is however managed by the takaful operator.

2. TAKAFUL OPERATING MODELS

The choice of takaful operating models largely depends on so many factors such as regional acceptance and regulatory framework. In Nigeria, the recognized models of takaful are three, namely: *mudarabah* (profit sharing), *wakalah* (agency), and hybrid *wakalah-mudarabah* (agency-profit sharing).²

Takaful operators are required to obtain the approval of NAICOM on the operating model they intend to use.³ Also, All the operating models and contracts must be presented for approval of NAICOM by the takaful operator after they are first approved by the takaful operator's Advisory Council of Experts (ACE) and the Board of Directors.⁴ If the takaful operator is implementing an operating model that is not in

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¹ RC Maysami, and WJ Kwon, Takaful and its Operational Guideline in Nigeria

² Paragraph 2.2 of the Takaful Operational Guidelines 2013

³ Paragraph 2.3 of the Takaful Operational Guidelines 2013

⁴ Paragraph 2.4 of the Takaful Operational Guidelines 2013

line with paragraph 2.2 of the Takaful Operational Guidelines 2013, or where it decides to change its operating model, it will require approval from NAICOM before further implementation.⁵

2.1 Mudarabah Model

Mudarabah is one of the major financial concepts of Islamic financial system. It is a contract whereby one party entrusts a sum of money or capital to another party called entrepreneur (*Mudarib*) to trade with for an agreed percentage of the profits. If there is any loss in the trade, the capital provider will bear it and the entrepreneur will have nothing for his efforts and time.⁶ This model is structured on profit sharing and loss bearing principles. i.e. partnership model, where the participants provide the capital and the takaful operator provides expertise and management of the fund.⁷ The *takaful* operator shares in the investments via a predetermined ratio mutually agreed with the participants. The takaful operator therefore performs the duty of both asset management and underwriting. Neither party can unilaterally alter the agreed sharing formula which is usually set out in the contract.⁸

The funds contributed by the participants into the takaful common pool and used for underwriting purposes are otherwise known as the Participants' Risk Fund (PRF). while the resources used for investment purposes are known as the Participants' Investment Fund (PIF).⁹ While the participants jointly own the PRE which is the risk pool solely applied for the purpose of mutual guarantee or settlement of claims, on the other hand, they own the PIF individually and separately.

From the participants' contribution to the common pool of funds, a part is invested as PIF and the other as PRF. which is used for the settlement of claims, for re-takaful purposes and as reserves.¹⁰ When the PIF is invested, the profit earned from such investment is shared between the takaful operator and the individual participants' bawd on a pre-agreed ratio depending on the takaful model adopted. The strategic

⁵ Paragraph 2.15 of the Takaful Operational Guidelines 2013

⁶ Aly Khorshid, *Islamic Insurance: A Modern Approach to Islamic Banking* (Routledge 2004)

⁷ *ibid*

⁸ *ibid*

⁹ MK Hassan and RN Kayed and UA Oseni *Introduction to Islamic Banking & Finance Principles and Practice*. Pearson Education Limited (2013)

¹⁰ *ibid*

position of the participants in the takaful business makes them both the capital providers as well as the owners of the whole takaful enterprise. But as the takaful undertaking involves both insurance coverage and investment, the takaful operator is considered a business partner of the participants when it comes to the investor-entrepreneur relationship under the *mudarabah* agreement.¹¹

It should be emphasized here that, the profit-and-loss bearing principle is based on *mudarabah* contract where the ratios of profit distribution are predetermined. The financial loss is borne by the capital providers (participants). On the other hand, the takaful operator may lose the rewards for the provided labour i.e the investment hinds run into deficit.

2.2 Wakalah Model

The *wakalah* model of takaful is basically based on the contract of agency between the takaful operator and the participants. Under this arrangement the participants pay contributions into a common fund which is delegated to the takaful operator who acts as an agent in the management and administration of the said fund for a prescribed fee clearly specified and agreed upon by the parties.

It should be noted that under this arrangement the takaful operator does not share in the risk nor in the surplus generated from the fund. It receives only a fixed fee to cover management expenses.¹² Any surplus realized from the investment of the participants' Funds under this arrangement goes to the participants only. This model therefore is a typical agency contract under which the principal-agent relationship is enforced which entitles the takaful operator to a fee or commission from the participants for its services as an agent. Similarly, apart from the normal agency fee, which is pre-agreed by the parties the takaful operator could be entitled to a performance-related fee which is given as a kind of incentive for prudent management.¹³

2.3 Hybrid of Mudarabah and Wakalah Models

This takaful model is a combination of the *mudarabah* and *wakalah* models. The two models are used for two different purposes in the takaful Fund. Under this

¹¹ *ibid*

¹² *ibid.*

¹³ *Ibid.*

arrangement, the *mudarabah* model is used specifically for the investment activities of the fund while the *wakalah* model is adopted for the underwriting activities.

The takaful operator plays a dual role under this model as both manager and agent. This entitles the takaful operator to a share in the profit in its role as manager of the takaful investment activities of the fund as well to an agreed scheduled commission or agency fee for its role as an agent of the participants in the underwriting activities respectively.

This twin role makes the hybrid model a unique one and is the reason why it is becoming a more popular model.¹⁴ Some of the reason for its popularity and acceptance is the fact that many scholars have adjudged it to be the most suitable and mutually beneficial model for all the parties concerned. The takaful operator's sources of income are larger and more diversified under this model, i.e. the agency fee, incentive fee, and the profit share from the investment of the funds. The Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) also recommends this model for takaful operators.

3. CATEGORIES OF TAKAFUL OPERATION

The Takaful Operational Guidelines, 2013 provide for two categories of takaful operations in Nigeria.¹⁵ These categories are, family and general takaful insurance.

Before explaining the two categories of takaful operations in Nigeria, it is very important to note that the takaful operational guidelines, 2013 made no provision for life insurance. This omission perhaps may not be unconnected with the controversy surrounding its permissibility under Islamic law. Many Islamic scholars have objected to the permissibility of life insurance for a number of reasons. Firstly, life insurance is viewed as an insurance against death, which would be unlawful under Islamic law, because life and death are in the hands of God. Secondly, the objection arises out of the conventional life insurance policy structure that allows an individual to appoint a nominee as a beneficiary of the policy upon death. This would seem to violate the Islamic law of inheritance (*miraath*) which outlines how a deceased person's estate is distributed.

¹⁴ *ibid*

¹⁵ *ibid*

For the purpose of this thesis therefore, consideration would be given to the two categories of takaful insurance recognized by the takaful operational guidelines 2013.

3.1 Family Takaful Insurance

Family takaful insurance is usually a long-term arrangement between the takaful insurance operator and the participants wherein a financial relief is provided by the takaful operator to the participants. For instance, this applies to cases of bereavement, critical illness or disabling injury.

Family takaful is also generally considered as the alternative to life insurance under conventional insurance. Under this arrangement, people come together to mutually indemnify one another against any disaster that may befall any member of their family, such as sudden death or permanent disability. As this form of takaful covers life and family issues, it is usually offered in a long-term arrangement that may span between 10 and 30 years depending on the structure of the product as well as the agreement of the parties.¹⁶

3.2 General Takaful Insurance

General takaful insurance on the other hand is a short-term arrangement between the takaful insurance operator and takaful insurance participants under which the takaful operator provides financial compensation for specified losses such as theft or damage etc. The takaful participants pay certain specified contributions while the takaful operator assumes the responsibility of managing the risk through the administration of the underwriting activities. A general takaful fund is established from the participants' contributions and the money invested in Shari'ah-complaint businesses. The proceeds that accrue from these investments are then returned to fund for the purpose of indemnifying the takaful participants. General takaful is also renewable periodically according to the terms and conditions of the takaful contract.¹⁷

4. BASIC DISTINCTIONS BETWEEN CONVENTIONAL AND TAKAFUL INSURANCE

¹⁶ M K Hassan and RB Kay ed and U A Oseni

¹⁷ *ibid*

Takaful is an alternative to the conventional system of insurance whereby participants contribute funds into a common pool based on the principles of ta'awun (mutual assistance) and tabarru' (donation) for the sole purpose of providing guarantee to one another for losses arising from specific risks.

The core principles of takaful are tabarru' (donation) and ta'awun (mutual assistance) as well as avoidance of *riba* (interest), *gharar* (uncertainty) and *maysir* (gambling).¹⁸ It is important to note that prohibition of all sources of unjustified enrichment is one of the most crucial teachings of Islam in its quest to establish justice and to eliminate exploitation in business. Therefore, there is clear prohibition against *riba*, *gharar* and *maysir*.¹⁹

Tabarru' as noted earlier, is a donation covenant where all participants agree to mutually support each other which forms the basis of their contributions into the takaful fund. Its main objective is for the benefit of the takaful participants. It is also the first stage in the structuring of a takaful transaction.

Ta'awun on the other hand, is the established Islamic concept of mutual assistance and it is the basis on which takaful participants willingly agree that the takaful insurance fund be used for the mutual benefit of all participants to meet eligible claims.²⁰ Therefore, the concept of *takaful* basically differ from conventional insurance in the sense that under the conventional system, the insured benefits from the cover and indemnity to be provided by the insurer, while the insurer benefits from the premium paid by the insured.²¹ Similarly, the element of mutuality which is at the center of takaful is absent in conventional insurance because the insurer views the insurance contract from a purely commercial perspective with its own risk and reward profile.

The concept of providing indemnity under takaful does not in any way involve commercial relationship between the takaful operator and the participant. In fact, the takaful operator is not an insurer as understood under conventional insurance, but

¹⁸ Islamic Financial Services Board (December 2009). Guideline Principles on Governance for Takaful (Islamic Insurance) Undertakings, Kuala Lumpur

¹⁹ MDAbdul Awwal Sarker, 'Islamic Business Contracts, Agency Problem and the Theory of the Islamic Firm', *International Journal of Islamic Financial Services* Vol. 1 No. 2

²⁰ Paragraph 1, 11 of the Takaful Operational Guidelines, 2013

²¹ *ibid.*

merely an operator who manages the takaful operations.²² The individual contributions or donations of each takaful participant are paid into the Participations' Risk Fund (PRF) out of which they (participants) provide mutual cover to each other. Unlike in the conventional insurance where policy holders buy the insurance cover and transfer the ownership of the premium they pay to the insurance company, takaful participants own the Participants' Investment Fund (PIF) and the takaful operator only manages the underwriting and investments on behalf of the participants for a predetermined fee²³

As described by AAOIFL, takaful insurance is “a symbiotic relationship between people who may be exposed to similar danger”.²⁴ This relationship is formed basically for the avoidance or mitigation of damage or losses caused by those dangers against which the participants pay contributions and from which compensation is paid to any member who suffers losses.

The basic distinctions between takaful and conventional insurance discussed hereunder are specifically in the area of contract, risk sharing and management, parties involved and the payment of premium. While the four basic distinctions would be discussed at a length, other differences would however be highlighted in brief.

5.0 CONTRACT FOR TAKAFUL

Takaful as a form of insurance is essentially a contract which like all contracts, is legally binding on the parties thereto based on obligations contained therein. The fundamentals required in a takaful contract are also mostly found in the general type of conventional contracts. These include the parties to the contract, their legal capacity, clear offer and emphatic acceptance, valuable consideration, an identifiable subject matter which should be legal and not contravene public morality, good faith, etc.

It is important at this point to highlight the concept of contract under Shari'ah with a view to having a better understanding of takaful contracts. Generally, the Arabic term

²²ibid

²³ ibid

²⁴ Islamic Sharia Standards No. 26 page 436

used to designate contract and convey the sense of undertaking and obligation is Aqd which is synonymous with the word contract found in modern law.²⁵ The word “Aqd” literally means “to tie”, “to fasten”, “to link”, “together”, “to bind”, “to pull hard” and “to strengthen”.²⁶

The Glorious Qur’an has used the word in different verses, thus:

- a. And resolve not on the marriage tie until the prescribed period (iddah) reaches its end.²⁷
- b. Allah will not call you to account for what is void in your oaths, but will call you to account for oath which you take in earnest.²⁸
- c. O you who believe Fulfil your contracts.²⁹

Technically, Aqd has been defined as the connection of an offer (ijab) emanating from one of the two contracting parties with the acceptance (qabul) of the other party in such a way that connotes an implication on the subject matter.³⁰ Therefore, a valid Shari’ah contract is built upon three essential elements, namely: the form of the contract, the subject matter and the contracting parties. These essential elements are to be fulfilled or satisfied completely so as to qualify a contract to be assigned with its prescribed legal effects.³¹

Form of the contract refers to an expression made by the contracting parties to declare their inner will to undertake a contract and thereafter be bound by certain obligations. This expression is manifested in an offer (ijab) made by the offeror and acceptance (qabul) made by the of the offeree. Ijab is a declaration that is made first with a view

²⁵MT Mansuri: *Islamic Law of Contracts and Business Transations*. (Adam Publishers & Distributors, New Delhi-110002, 2007)

²⁶ YY Bambale, *Islamic Commercial and Industrial Transactions* (Malthous Press Limited, 2007)

²⁷ Qur’an, 2:235

²⁸ Qur’an, 5 :89

²⁹ Qur’an 5 :1

³⁰ MOBasha, *Marshid al-Hayran ‘ila Ma’rtah Ahwal Al-insan* (1990) eghpt: Nazzarah al-Umumiyyah, page : 65 : Islamic Fionancial System. Principles and Operations, International Shari’ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance

³¹ ibid

to creating an obligation: it is of three kinds, namely: kalam (verbal), amal (by conduct) and kitabah (in writing).³²

On the other hand, qabul is simply an acceptance which always determines a legally binding agreement under Islamic law of contract. Like ijab, qabul can also be verbal, by conduct or in writing. Worthy of note is that qabul must always be either in the present or past tense but certainly not in the future tense.³³

6. THE GENERAL RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE NATIONAL INSURANCE COMMISSION (NAICOM)

The National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) was established in 1997 by the Government of Nigeria with the primary responsibility of regulating and supervising insurance business in Nigeria. NAICOM replaces the then regulatory body called The Nigerian Insurance Supervisory Board. Before the coming of the NAICOM, the federal ministry of finance was responsible for licensing of insurance companies. Generally, NAICOM as a regulatory body for all insurance companies in Nigeria has among others the following functions; administer, supervise, regulate and control the Nigerian Insurance Industry in order to protect insurance consumers and support financial stability. NAICOM has after its establishment been ensuring compliance with all legal and regulatory requirements including capital adequacy, sound and prudent management, standards for conduct of insurance business in Nigeria and the protection of the general public.

7. CONCLUSION

An insurance contract is basically considered as mandatory agreement between parties which binds them upon completion of certain legal actions. Consequently, neither party may break its contractual obligations. This means that in a conventional insurance contract, while the insured party is duly obligated to pay an agreed premium to the insurer on contractually specified dates, the insurer on the other hand is also obligated to indemnify the insured upon the happening of the insured incident. A major distinction between this arrangement under conventional insurance and the

³² ³² NS Bin Abdullah, Formation of Contract under Vienna Sale convention and Islamic Law: A comparative Study in Vanconver Journal of International Business and Law

³³ibid

takaful insurance is that the two commitments are not equal. This is because, under conventional insurance, while the insured makes a commitment to pay a fixed premium on a fixed date based on an unknown and undefined possibility, this possibility is uncertain in both time and cost. Regardless of this, the insured under the conventional system is still under obligation to pay the agreed amount on time. Similarly, as opposed to being fixed, the insurer's commitment is also merely probable as far as time and cost are concerned, since the incident may or may not occur. The insurer could therefore pay the agreed compensation either in full or in part depending on the circumstance. In a situation where the incident wholly occurs, the insurer makes full indemnity. If the incident partly occurs, then the insurer pays in part. In cases where the incident does not occur at all, the insurer pays nothing to the insured.

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In contrast, takaful adopts an entirely different concept. This is because shari'ah requires that a contract of interchange which makes provision for exchanging protection for a premium must be free from all uncertainties in the counter values.³⁵ Similarly, the insurance industry is unlikely to be devoid of uncertainties because uncertainties are peculiar and integral to both premium and compensation. It is because of this that the first global fatwa issued for Islamic insurance required that takaful contract be based on a tabarru' (donation) contract. The concept of tabarru' was also adopted based on a fiqhi (Islamic jurisprudence) maxim which says 'Uncertainties are tolerable in gratuitous contracts'³⁶ the contract of tabarru' is considered valid and enforceable in Islamic commercial law even for no consideration because it is gratuitous and is aimed at giving favour to the recipient without any consideration.

Tabarru' is derived from the Arabic word tabarra'a which means gift, donation, contribution or charity.³⁷ Technically, the concept of tabarru' refers to a unilateral declaration of intent aimed at favouring a recipient without any specific consideration

³⁴ Al Thanayan. S (1993). *Insurance and its Provisions*, (Dar ibu Hazim for Publishing, Edition, 2003) Beirut,

³⁵ *ibid*

³⁶ *ibid*

³⁷ Tabarru and Takaful Global Islamic Finance Report (GIFR) 2021, 136

in return.³⁸ Tabarru' essentially comprises of 2 (two) pillars; the absence of a counter value and the deration for the donation made to him.

Therefore, based on the concept of takaful which represents a common relationship of mutual help between the participating members who undertake to jointly indemnify each other in the event of a defined incident. It is hereby recommended that the government should energize and give more powers to NAICOM to include prosecutorial powers to prosecute companies that are involved in insurance practice violations, the government should also make it mandatory that every insurable person and interest take up insurance policy and the government should ensure that qualified persons are appointed to head NAICOM as an organization. intention to donate.³⁹ In its original form therefore, tabarru is gratuitous in nature. Uncertainties are eliminated under the tabarru contract because the donor voluntarily makes the donation and the recipient receives same for no consideration. The issue of non-satisfaction of the contract also does not arise as the recipient never paid any consideration.

³⁸ *ibid*

³⁹ *ibid*